

Managing Digitalization: Challenges and Opportunities for Business

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Digitalization is a fundamental agent of transition for most kinds of businesses. However, digitalization is not a unitary issue. Instead, it takes place and provides opportunities and threats on different dimensions that can be approached in different ways.

One dimension of digitalization are operations in companies and beyond. Digital processes, efficiency or productivity of employees are aspects thereof. An example may be the connection of interfaces and computer systems to become more efficient. Another dimension is digital customer experience. That a company can improve the understanding of its customers' needs it is key to analyse the data of the customer journey and to adjust digital tools of e-commerce accordingly.

Characteristics like trust to the tool or simplicity are other aspects of customer experience. A further dimension are social aspects like leadership competences in a digital environment. As an exemplifying aspect, the error-culture can be mentioned. In an error-culture errors are accepted because they are seen as a means for improvement and thus for success. Another aspect, to mention just one more, is agile management what basically means the flexibility to approach necessary changes anticipating and fast.

To manage digitalization means, moreover to understand the own company as a part of an ecosystem or network in which different stakeholders are related to each other. Through digital platforms (like e.g. LinkedIn), individual networks of employees become more important. Such platforms support the blurring of company borders as well as decentralization: it is becoming more unclear what belongs to a company and what does not. Under these circumstances individual, (sub)divisional or project-based contacts and networks are gaining relevance. The network character is elementary and has

to be considered when managing digitalization and seeking opportunities. These is in a nutshell the thematic field of this special issue.

The selected papers for this issue are a collection of contributions submitted to the MakeLearn & TIME international conference held from 17 to 19 May 2017 in Lublin, Poland. The subject of the special issue can be seen as a specified part of the conference's topic, which was about the management of challenges in a networked society.

In the first paper, Martti Saarela, Daniel Örtqvist, Anna-Mari Simunaniemi, and Matti Muhos state that digitalization can revolutionise healthcare services and thus provide new business opportunities for innovative start-ups. They are interested in what are the critical incidents related to the early development stages of eHealth service start-ups. These early stages are said by authors to be decisive for the survival of a business. Based on semi-structured interviews and the Critical Incident Technique (CIT) 14 eHealth service start-ups in Sweden and Finland are examined.

The second paper is written by Bistra Vassileva. It is concerned with consumer behavioural models and aims to understand reactions of consumers to social network marketing. Reactions to social network marketing are explored in the paper based on the three criteria Level of brand engagement, word-of-mouth referral behaviour and purchase intentions. Data were gathered from 700 Bulgarian respondents. A factor and cluster analysis are applied. Overall, results show that consumers are willing to receive marketing information via social networks.

The purpose of the paper from Tomasz Szczepanik, Beata Skowron-Grabowska, Joanna Nowakowska-Grunt, and Anna Brzozowska is to identify the impact of information systems of logistic centres on services of courier companies when courier companies can use these information systems. Thereto in the third paper, a class of information systems of logistic centres used by courier companies are presented and considered. The results show which IT systems of logistic centres are of use for the courier companies. Moreover, results provide insights how the use of these IT systems in courier companies affects the information flow in their services.

The fourth paper is from Narasimha Rao Vajjhala and Salu George Thandekkattu and examines why the adoption of e-commerce has been slow and limited in Small and medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), especially in transition economies. Based on a qualitative-inductive approach the authors analyse 30 interviews, which they conducted with managers from SMEs in Albania. They identified four key barrier factors: resource constraints, external environmental factors, or-

ganizational issues and resistance to accept new technologies. The findings can help to approach the adoption of e-commerce in transition countries.

In the fifth paper, Tuulia Nikunen, Martti Saarela, Eeva-Liisa Oikarinen, Matti Muhos, and Lari Isohella declare digital marketing to be a vitally important opportunity for micro-enterprises. Its goal therefore is to contribute to a more in-depth understanding of micro-enterprises' current strategies concerning new digital marketing tools that foster stronger customer relationships. Based on interviews with two marketing service providers the paper describes how micro-enterprise clients use digital marketing to foster customer relationships. Results show that the practical understanding of digital marketing tools is of a high importance.

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